

$$\Phi = \frac{(1+m^2)^{1/2} Q(F)}{r} + U\left(\frac{1}{r}\right)$$

(Id/v)

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\Phi}}{\partial v} = \rho \tilde{\Psi} \rightarrow \left(\frac{\partial x^a}{\partial v}\right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^a} \tilde{\Phi}\right) = \rho \tilde{\Psi} \Rightarrow \boxed{m^a \partial_a \tilde{\Phi} = \rho \tilde{\Psi}}$$

$$\boxed{m^a = \frac{x^a}{r}}$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^a} \tilde{\Phi}\right) \stackrel{m^a}{=} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^a} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\Phi}}{\partial r}\right) = \frac{x_a}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{(1+m^2)^{1/2} Q(F)}{r} + U\left(\frac{1}{r}\right) \right] = \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{\alpha^{1/2} Q(F)}{r} \right] + U'(r) =$$

$$\boxed{r = (x_m x^m)^{1/2}}$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial r}{\partial x^a}\right] = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x_m x^m}} \cdot 2x_m \delta_a^m = \boxed{\frac{x_a}{r}}$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{\alpha^{1/2} Q(F)}{r} \right] + U'(r) = \boxed{\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{\alpha^{1/2} Q(F)}{r} \right] + U'(r)}$$

$$\tilde{\Psi} = \frac{x_a}{r} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^a} \tilde{\Phi} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{\alpha^{1/2} Q(F)}{r} \right] = \boxed{\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{\alpha^{1/2} Q(F)}{r} \right]}$$

$$\int_{v \rightarrow 1} \sqrt{g'} d\theta^1 d\theta^2 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \tilde{\Psi} \right] = \int_{v \rightarrow 1} \frac{\alpha^{1/2} d\theta^1 d\theta^2}{(1 - \frac{m}{r})} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{\alpha^{1/2} Q(F)}{r} \right] \right) \cong \ominus \alpha^{1/2} Q(F) \int dS^{(2)} = \boxed{\ominus \Omega_{(2)} \alpha^{1/2} Q(F)}$$

$$\int_{v \rightarrow 1} \sqrt{g'} d\theta^1 d\theta^2 \left[\sqrt{g'} \tilde{\Psi} \cdot \underline{v} \right] = \int_{v \rightarrow 1} r^2 d\theta^1 d\theta^2 \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\frac{\alpha^{1/2} Q(F)}{r} \right] \right) \left(\frac{1 - \frac{m}{r}}{r} \right) \cong \boxed{\ominus \Omega_{(2)} \alpha^{1/2} Q(F)}$$

$$\alpha^{1/2} \doteq \sqrt{1+m^2}$$

$$\int_{v \rightarrow 1} \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\delta} d\theta^1 d\theta^2 = \int_{v \rightarrow 1} \frac{r^2}{m} dS^{(2)} = m \int dS^{(2)} = \boxed{\Omega_{(2)} m}$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g'} \frac{\gamma \phi \psi}{\rho} \ominus \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right\} = \ominus \frac{1}{V} (\gamma \phi \cdot \phi^{1a})_{,a} \right]$$

$$\int \int \int \sqrt{g'} d\theta^1 d\theta^2 dV$$

(Id/8)

$$\int \int \int \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g'} \frac{\gamma \phi \psi}{\rho} \ominus \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right\} = \ominus \int \int \int \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{V} (\gamma \phi \cdot \phi^{1a})_{,a} * \sqrt{g'} d\theta^1 d\theta^2 dV$$

$$\int \int \sqrt{g'} d\theta^1 d\theta^2$$

$$\int \int \left(\frac{\sqrt{g'}}{V} \phi \cdot \psi \ominus \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right) \underbrace{\sqrt{g'} d\theta^1 d\theta^2}_{dS} = 0$$

$$\int_{v_1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{g'}}{V} \phi \cdot \psi \ominus \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right) dS \ominus \int_{v_0} \left(\frac{\sqrt{g'}}{V} \phi \cdot \psi \ominus \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right) dS = 0$$

$$\int_{v_1} \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{V} \phi \cdot \psi dS \ominus \int_{v_0} \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{V} \phi \cdot \psi dS \ominus \int_{v_1} \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\rho} dS + \int_{v_0} \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\rho} dS = 0$$

$$\frac{S_0}{\rho_0} \ominus \phi_0 \int_{v_0} \frac{\psi}{V} dS = \int_{v_1} \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\rho} dS$$

$\rho \sim \frac{r^2}{m}$ $\sqrt{g'} \sim r^2$ $\Rightarrow \int \frac{r^2}{r^2} m dS = m \Omega_2$
 Eq. (57) Israel!

$$\ominus \phi_0 \left(\int_{v_0} \frac{\psi}{V} dS \right) + \frac{S_0}{\rho_0} = m \Omega_2 \rightarrow \text{obj.}$$

$$\boxed{(\gamma\phi^2 + v^2)_{,a}} = 2\gamma\phi \cdot \phi_{,a} + 2v \cdot \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x^a}\right) = 2\gamma\phi \cdot \phi_{,a} + \frac{2v \cdot m_a}{\rho}$$

(I/4)

$$m_a = \rho \frac{\partial v}{\partial x^a} \Rightarrow \boxed{\frac{\partial v}{\partial x^a}} = \frac{m_a}{\rho}$$

$$\ominus \left(\frac{\rho \cdot \phi^{1a}}{v} (\gamma\phi^2 + v^2) \ominus \frac{(\gamma\phi^2 + v^2)_{,a} \cdot (\rho \phi^{1a})}{v} \right) = \ominus \frac{(\rho \phi^{1a})_{,a}}{v} (\gamma\phi^2 + v^2) \ominus \left[2\gamma\phi \cdot \phi_{,a} + \frac{2v \cdot m_a}{\rho} \right] \frac{\rho \phi^{1a}}{v}$$

$$= \ominus \frac{(\rho \phi^{1a})_{,a}}{v} (\gamma\phi^2 + v^2) \ominus \frac{2\gamma\phi \cdot \phi_{,a} \cdot \rho \phi^{1a}}{v} \ominus \left(\frac{2v m_a \cdot \rho \phi^{1a}}{\rho v} \right) \rightarrow \boxed{m_a \cdot e^a_{(a)} = 0}$$

$$\boxed{\ominus \frac{(\rho \phi^{1a})_{,a}}{v} (\gamma\phi^2 + v^2) \ominus \frac{2\gamma\rho\phi \cdot \phi_{,a} \phi^{1a}}{v}} \Downarrow$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} (\gamma\phi^2 + v) \frac{\psi}{v} \ominus \frac{2\phi \sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right] = \ominus \frac{1}{v} \left[(\gamma\phi^2 + v^2) \cdot \rho \phi^{1a} \right]_{,a}}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} (\gamma \phi^2 + v^2) \frac{\psi}{v} \ominus \frac{2\phi \sqrt{g}'}{\rho} \right]} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi}{v} \right] \cdot (\gamma \phi^2 + v^2) + \sqrt{g} \frac{\psi}{v} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\gamma \phi^2 + v^2) \ominus \frac{2}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\phi) \cdot \frac{\sqrt{g}'}{\rho} +$$

$$\oplus 2\phi \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{\sqrt{g}'}{\rho} \right) \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \right) =$$

(I/3)

$$= \ominus \frac{(\rho \cdot \phi^{1a})_{,a}}{v} \cdot (\gamma \phi^2 + v^2) + \frac{\psi}{v} (\gamma 2\phi \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} + 2v) \ominus \frac{2}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\phi) + 2\phi \left[\ominus \frac{\gamma \rho'}{v} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{1a}) \right] =$$

$$= \ominus \frac{(\rho \cdot \phi^{1a})_{,a}}{v} (\gamma \phi^2 + v^2) + 2\gamma \frac{\psi \phi}{v} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} + \frac{2\psi \cdot v}{v} \ominus 2\psi \ominus \frac{2\phi \gamma \rho'}{v} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{1a}) =$$

$$= \ominus \frac{(\rho \cdot \phi^{1a})_{,a}}{v} (\gamma \phi^2 + v^2) + 2\gamma \cdot \frac{\psi \phi}{v} \rho \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} \right) + \frac{2\psi \ominus 2\psi}{v} \ominus \frac{2\gamma \phi \rho \psi^2}{v} \ominus \frac{2\phi \gamma \rho}{v} \phi_{,a} \phi^{1a} =$$

$$= \ominus \frac{(\rho \cdot \phi^{1a})_{,a}}{v} (\gamma \phi^2 + v^2) + \frac{2\gamma \rho \psi \phi^2}{v} \ominus \frac{2\gamma \rho \psi^2 \phi}{v} \ominus \frac{2\phi \gamma \rho}{v} \phi_{,a} \phi^{1a} =$$

$$\boxed{= \ominus \frac{(\rho \cdot \phi^{1a})_{,a}}{v} (\gamma \phi^2 + v^2) \ominus \frac{2\phi \gamma \rho}{v} \phi_{,a} \phi^{1a}}$$

$$\textcircled{1} \quad \boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\ominus \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right]} = \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial (\sqrt{g})}{\partial v} \frac{1}{\rho} \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \sqrt{g} = \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \cdot \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial (\sqrt{g})}{\partial v} \ominus \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) = \textcircled{\mathbb{I}/2}$$

$$= \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial (\sqrt{g})}{\partial v} + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} \quad \parallel \quad \boxed{\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} = \sqrt{g} \rho K}$$

$$= \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{1}{\rho} [\sqrt{g} \rho K] + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} = \ominus K + \textcircled{\frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v}} \quad \parallel \quad \boxed{\frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} = K \ominus \frac{\gamma \rho}{\sqrt{g}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a})}$$

$$= \ominus K + K \ominus \frac{\gamma \rho}{\sqrt{g}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a}) = \boxed{\ominus \frac{\gamma \rho}{\sqrt{g}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a})}$$

$$\textcircled{2} \quad \boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\sqrt{g} \psi}{\sqrt{v}} \cdot \gamma \phi \right]} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\sqrt{g} \psi}{\sqrt{v}} \right] \cdot \gamma \phi + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\sqrt{g} \psi}{\sqrt{v}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\gamma \phi) = \ominus (\rho \cdot \phi^{,a})_{,a} \cdot \gamma \phi +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \psi \cdot \gamma \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} \right) = \ominus (\rho \cdot \phi^{,a})_{,a} \cdot \gamma \phi +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \psi \cdot \gamma \cdot \rho \psi = \ominus (\rho \cdot \phi^{,a})_{,a} \cdot \gamma \phi +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \gamma \rho \cdot \psi^2$$

$$\textcircled{1} + \textcircled{2} = \ominus (\rho \cdot \phi^{,a})_{,a} \cdot \gamma \phi + \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \rho \gamma \psi^2 \ominus \frac{\gamma \rho}{\sqrt{g}} \psi^2 \ominus \frac{\gamma \rho \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a}}{\sqrt{g}} =$$

$$= \ominus (\rho \cdot \phi^{,a})_{,a} \cdot \gamma \phi \ominus \frac{\gamma \rho \cdot \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a}}{\sqrt{g}} = \boxed{\ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} (\rho \cdot \phi^{,a} \cdot \gamma \phi)_{,a}}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g}' \left(\frac{F(v, \phi)}{v} \cdot \psi + \frac{G(v, \phi)}{\rho} \right) \right] = \underbrace{A \cdot (\psi^2 + \phi_{1a} \cdot \phi^{1a}) + B \cdot \psi + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v}}_{\downarrow 0} \ominus \frac{1}{v} [F \cdot \rho \cdot \phi^{1a}]_{,a} \quad \textcircled{I/1}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g}' \left(F(v, \phi) \cdot \frac{\psi}{v} + \frac{G(v, \phi)}{\rho} \right) \right] = \ominus \frac{1}{v} [F \cdot \rho \cdot \phi^{1a}]_{,a}}$$

$$\textcircled{1} \boxed{F=1, G=0}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g}' \frac{\psi}{v} \right] = \ominus \left(\frac{\rho \phi^{1a}}{v} \right)_{,a}}$$

$$\textcircled{2} \boxed{F=\gamma\phi, G=-1}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g}' \left(\gamma\phi \cdot \frac{\psi}{v} \right) + \frac{\sqrt{g}'}{\rho} (\ominus 1) \right] = \ominus \frac{1}{v} [(\gamma\phi) \cdot \rho \cdot \phi^{1a}]_{,a}}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} = \rho\psi} \quad \boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g}' \frac{\psi}{v} \right] = \ominus (\rho \cdot \phi^{1a})_{,a};}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} = K \ominus \frac{\gamma}{v} \rho (\psi^2 + \phi_{1a} \cdot \phi^{1a})}$$

$$\textcircled{3} \boxed{F=\gamma\phi^2+v^2, G=\ominus 2\phi}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g}' \left((\gamma\phi^2+v^2) \cdot \frac{\psi}{v} + \frac{\ominus 2\phi}{\rho} \right) \right] = \ominus \frac{1}{v} [(\gamma\phi^2+v^2) \cdot \rho \cdot \phi^{1a}]_{,a}}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \left(\frac{F_1(v, \phi_1)}{\sqrt{v}} \psi_1 + \frac{F_2(v, \phi_2)}{\sqrt{v}} \psi_2 + \frac{G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2)}{\rho} \right) \right] =$$

(Id/2)

$$= \frac{\rho}{\sqrt{v}} \left[G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2) (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a}^2 + \phi_{2,a}^2) + \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial \phi_1} (\psi_1^2 + \phi_{1,a}^2) + \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial \phi_2} (\psi_2^2 + \phi_{2,a}^2) \right]$$

$$+ \psi_1 \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial v} (v, \phi_1) + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_1} \right] + \psi_2 \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial v} (v, \phi_2) + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_2} \right] + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} (v, \phi_1, \phi_2) +$$

$$\ominus \left(\rho \phi_1^{1a} \cdot F_1(v, \phi_1) \right)_{,a} \ominus \left(\rho \phi_2^{1a} \cdot F_2(v, \phi_2) \right)_{,a}$$

To get integral conservation laws we have to have:

$$\textcircled{1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial v} (v, \phi_1) + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_1} (v, \phi_1, \phi_2) = 0$$

$$\textcircled{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial v} (v, \phi_2) + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_2} (v, \phi_1, \phi_2) = 0$$

$$\textcircled{3} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} (v, \phi_1, \phi_2) = 0$$

$$\textcircled{4} G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2) (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a}^2 + \phi_{2,a}^2) + \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial \phi_1} (\psi_1^2 + \phi_{1,a}^2) + \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial \phi_2} (\psi_2^2 + \phi_{2,a}^2) = 0$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \left(\frac{F_1(v, \phi_1)}{v} \psi_1 + \frac{F_2(v, \phi_2)}{v} \psi_2 + \frac{G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2)}{p} \right) \right] =$$

Ed/6

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\rho \phi_2^a \cdot F_2(v, \phi_2))_{,a}$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{\rho \phi_1^a \cdot F_1(v, \phi_1)}{v} \right)_{,a} + \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{\rho \phi_2^a \cdot F_2(v, \phi_2)}{v} \right)_{,a} +$$

$$+ \frac{\psi_1}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F_1(v, \phi_1) + \frac{\psi_2}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F_2(v, \phi_2) + \frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_1} \cdot \psi_1 + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_2} \cdot \psi_2 \right) + \frac{1}{p} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} (v, \phi_1, \phi_2) +$$

$$+ \frac{G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2)}{v} (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a} + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}) + \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial \phi_1} (\phi_1^{1a} \phi_{1,a} + \psi_1^2) + \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial \phi_2} (\phi_2^{1a} \phi_{2,a} + \psi_2^2) +$$

$$+ \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial \phi_1} (\phi_1^{1a} \phi_{1,a} + \psi_1^2) + \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial \phi_2} (\phi_2^{1a} \phi_{2,a} + \psi_2^2) =$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\rho \phi_1^a \cdot F_1(v, \phi_1))_{,a}$$

$$= \frac{1}{v} \left[G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2) (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a} + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}) + \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial \phi_1} (\psi_1^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a}) + \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial \phi_2} (\psi_2^2 + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}) \right]$$

$$= \frac{G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2)}{v} (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a} + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}) + \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial \phi_1} (\psi_1^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a}) + \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial \phi_2} (\psi_2^2 + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}) +$$

$$+ \psi_1 \left[\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F_1(v, \phi_1) + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_1} \right] + \psi_2 \left[\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F_2(v, \phi_2) + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_2} \right] + \frac{1}{p} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} (v, \phi_1, \phi_2)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\rho \phi_1^a \cdot F_1(v, \phi_1))_{,a} + \frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\rho \phi_2^a \cdot F_2(v, \phi_2))_{,a}$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} = \rho \psi_1 \quad ; \quad \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial v} = \rho \psi_2$$

(I/5)

$$\frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} = K \ominus \frac{K \rho}{v} (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a} + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\ominus \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right] = \ominus \frac{\rho}{v} [\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a} + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}]$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_1}{v} \right] = \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_2}{v} \right] = \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \left[\phi_1 \cdot \frac{\psi_1}{v} + \phi_2 \cdot \frac{\psi_2}{v} \right] \ominus \frac{1}{\rho} \right] = \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \cdot \phi_{i,a} \cdot \phi_i^{1a})_{,a} + \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \phi_2 \cdot \phi_2^{1a})_{,a}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \left(\phi_1 + \frac{\psi_1}{v} \right) + \sqrt{g} \left(\phi_2 + \frac{\psi_2}{v} \right) \ominus \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right] =$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \uparrow \\ \tilde{F}_i = \phi_i, \quad G = \ominus 1 \\ \uparrow \\ i = 1, 2 \end{array} \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_1}{v} \right) \cdot \phi_1 + \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} \cdot \frac{\psi_1}{v} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_2}{v} \right) \cdot \phi_2 + \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial v} \cdot \frac{\psi_2}{v} \oplus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\ominus \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right] =$$

$$= \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a} \phi_1 + \frac{\rho}{v} \left(\frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} \right) \psi_1 \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a} \phi_2 + \frac{1 \cdot \rho}{v \rho} \left(\frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial v} \right) \psi_2 +$$

$$\ominus \frac{\rho}{v} (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a} + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}) = \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a} \phi_1 + \frac{\rho \psi_1^2}{v} \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a} \phi_2 + \frac{\rho \psi_2^2}{v} +$$

$$\ominus \frac{\rho}{v} (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2) \ominus \frac{\rho}{v} (\phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a}) \ominus \frac{\rho}{v} (\phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}) = \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a} \phi_1 \ominus \frac{\rho}{v} \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a} + \boxed{\ominus \frac{1}{v} (\phi_1 \rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a}} \\ \ominus \frac{1}{v} (\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a} \phi_2 \ominus \frac{\rho}{v} \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a} \quad \boxed{\ominus \frac{1}{v} (\phi_2 \rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a}}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2) \right] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} \right] \cdot \frac{G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2)}{\rho} \ominus \frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2)}{\partial v} \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \sqrt{g} \cdot G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2) =$$

$$= \ominus \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) = + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v}$$

$$= \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} K \right] \cdot \frac{G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2)}{\rho} \ominus \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} \oplus \left[\frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} \right] G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2) =$$

$$= \ominus K \cdot G(v, \phi_i) \ominus \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G(v, \phi_i)}{\partial v} + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} \cdot G(v, \phi_i) =$$

$$= \left[K G(v, \phi_i) \ominus \frac{\rho}{V} (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1, \alpha} \phi_1'^{\alpha} + \phi_{2, \alpha} \phi_2'^{\alpha}) G(v, \phi_i) \right]$$

$$= \left[\ominus \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} (v, \phi_i) \ominus \frac{\rho}{V} (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1, \alpha} \phi_1'^{\alpha} + \phi_{2, \alpha} \phi_2'^{\alpha}) G(v, \phi_i) \right]$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} \frac{G(v, \phi_i)}{\rho} \right] = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} (v, \phi_i) + \frac{\rho}{V} (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1, \alpha} \phi_1'^{\alpha} + \phi_{2, \alpha} \phi_2'^{\alpha})$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} F_i(v, \phi_i) \frac{\psi_i}{V} \right] = \ominus \frac{(\rho \phi_i'^{\alpha})_{, \alpha}}{V} \cdot F_i(v, \phi_i) + \frac{\psi_i}{V} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F_i(v, \phi_i)$$

on the other hand,

$$\left[\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} \right] = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_1} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_2} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial v} =$$

$$= \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_1} (\psi_1) + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi_2} (\psi_2)$$

↑ this condition should be added !!!

$$\frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} = \rho \psi_1 ; \quad \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial v} = \rho \psi_2$$

(7/4)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_1}{v} \right] &= \ominus (\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_2}{v} \right] &= \ominus (\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

$$\frac{\partial (\sqrt{g})}{\partial v} = \sqrt{g} \rho \cdot K$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} = K \ominus \frac{\rho}{v} (\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^a + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} F_1(v, \phi_1) \frac{\psi_1}{v} \right] &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_1}{v} \right] F_1(v, \phi_1) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \sqrt{g} \cdot \frac{\psi_1}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F_1(v, \phi_1) \\ &= \ominus (\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a} F_1(v, \phi_1) + \frac{\psi_1}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F_1(v, \phi_1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} F_2(v, \phi_2) \frac{\psi_2}{v} \right] &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_2}{v} \right] F_2(v, \phi_2) + \frac{\psi_2}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F_2(v, \phi_2) \\ &= \ominus (\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a} F_2(v, \phi_2) + \frac{\psi_2}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F_2(v, \phi_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2) \right] = \frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2) + \sqrt{g} \frac{\partial G(v, \phi_1, \phi_2)}{\partial v}$$

$$\boxed{(\rho \phi^{1a} \cdot F(V, \phi))_{,a} = (\rho \phi^{1a})_{,a} \cdot F(V, \phi) + \rho \phi^{1a} \frac{\partial F(V, \phi)}{\partial x^a}} \quad \textcircled{IdB}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \phi^{1a} \frac{\partial F(V, \phi)}{\partial x^a} &= \rho \phi^{1a} \left[\frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial V} \frac{\partial V}{\partial x^a} \right] = \rho \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} + \rho \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} \frac{\partial F}{\partial V} \frac{\partial V}{\partial x^a} = \\ &= \rho \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \phi^{1a} \phi_{,a} + \rho \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial V} \right) \frac{\partial V}{\partial x^a} \\ & \quad \rho \cdot \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial V} \underbrace{\left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial x^a} \right) \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial x^a} \right)}_{= \frac{1}{\rho^2}} \cdot \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial V} \\ &= \rho \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \psi^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{(\rho \phi^{1a} F(V, \phi))_{,a} = (\rho \phi^{1a})_{,a} F(V, \phi) + \rho \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} (\phi^{1a} \phi_{,a} + \psi^2)}$$

$$\boxed{(\rho \phi^{1a})_{,a} F(V, \phi) = (\rho \phi^{1a} \cdot F(V, \phi))_{,a} \ominus \rho \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} (\phi^{1a} \phi_{,a} + \psi^2)}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial V} \left(\sqrt{g} \left(\frac{F(V, \phi) \psi}{V} + \frac{g(V, \phi)}{f} \right) \right) = \boxed{A(V, \phi) \rho \cdot (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{1a})} + \boxed{B(V, \phi) \psi} + \boxed{\frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial g}{\partial V}} + \ominus \frac{1}{V} [F(V, \phi) \cdot \rho \cdot \phi_{,a}]^{1a}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} AV &= g + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \\ B &= \frac{1}{V} \frac{\partial F}{\partial V} + \frac{\partial g}{\partial \phi} \end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{A = B = \frac{\partial g}{\partial V} = 0} \Rightarrow \underline{\text{we get subyol conservation laws}}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} G(v, \phi) \right] = \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} \right] \cdot \frac{G(v, \phi)}{\rho} \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} \cdot \frac{1}{\rho} \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \sqrt{g} G(v, \phi) = \quad (\text{Id/2})$$

$$= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\sqrt{g}) = \sqrt{g} \rho K \right] = \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} \rho K \right] \cdot \frac{G(v, \phi)}{\rho} + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} \cdot G(v, \phi) \ominus \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} \quad \# \frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v}$$

$\frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\sqrt{g} G(v, \phi)) = \sqrt{g} \rho K + \sqrt{g} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v}$

$$= \ominus K \cdot G(v, \phi) + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} G(v, \phi) = \ominus K \cdot G(v, \phi) + K \cdot G(v, \phi) \ominus \frac{\gamma \rho G(v, \phi)}{\sqrt{v}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a}) \ominus \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G(v, \phi)}{\partial v}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} = K \ominus \frac{\gamma \rho}{\sqrt{v}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a})$$

$$= \frac{\ominus \gamma \rho G(v, \phi)}{\sqrt{v}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a}) \ominus \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G(v, \phi)}{\partial v}$$

$$\Rightarrow \ominus \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v} = \ominus \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} \right) = \ominus \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi} \cdot \psi$$

$$= \frac{\ominus \gamma \rho G(v, \phi)}{\sqrt{v}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a}) \ominus \frac{\partial G}{\partial \phi} \cdot \psi \quad \ominus \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial G}{\partial v}$$

*we add it!
anybody catches?*

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} F(v, \phi) \frac{\psi}{\sqrt{v}} \right] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} \frac{\psi}{\sqrt{v}} \right] F(v, \phi) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} \frac{\psi}{\sqrt{v}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F(v, \phi) =$$

$$= \frac{\ominus (\gamma \phi^{,a})_{,a}}{\sqrt{v}}$$

$$= \frac{\ominus (\gamma \phi^{,a})_{,a}}{\sqrt{v}} F(v, \phi) + \frac{\psi}{\sqrt{v}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F(v, \phi)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} = \rho \psi; \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi}{v} \right] = \ominus \frac{(p\phi)_{,a}}{v}$$

modified

$$\frac{1}{\rho v} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} = K \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a})$$

I'll modify this one!

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\sqrt{g} \psi) = \sqrt{g} \rho K \psi + \dots \right) \quad \rho = \rho_0 \quad \text{Id/h}$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial v} \cdot \phi + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} \cdot F$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial v} \cdot \phi + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} \cdot F$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\sqrt{g} \psi}{\rho} \right] = \ominus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a})$$

modified $\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} = \left(\frac{\partial x^a}{\partial v} \right) \cdot \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a}$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{F(v, \phi)}{v} \right] = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi}{v} \right] \right) F(v, \phi) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \sqrt{g} \frac{\psi}{v} \frac{\partial F}{\partial v}(v, \phi)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} \right) = \frac{\partial F}{\partial x^a}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{g(\phi, v)}{\rho} \right] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right] \cdot g(\phi, v) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} g(\phi, v) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right] g(\phi, v) + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} g(\phi, v)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{p F(v, \phi) \cdot \phi^a}{v} \right) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \cdot \frac{F(v, \phi) \psi}{v} \right] = 0 \quad \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} = \psi$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial v} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \phi} \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} \right) + \frac{\partial g}{\partial \rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial v} \right)$$

$$= \ominus \frac{(p\phi^a)_{,a}}{v} \cdot F(v, \phi) + \psi \left(\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} F(v, \phi) \right)$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial x^a} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a}$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial v} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v} \right) \psi$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} \cdot \frac{\partial x^a}{\partial v} = \rho \psi$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} (\psi^2 + \phi_{,a} \phi^{,a}) \frac{g(\phi, v)}{\rho} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} g(\phi, v)$$

$$(p F \phi^a)_{,a} = (p \phi^a)_{,a} F(v, \phi) + (p \phi^a) \cdot F_{,a} = \rho \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial x^a} \right) = \rho \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} \right) \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} = \rho \frac{\partial F}{\partial \phi} (\phi_{,a} \phi^{,a})$$

$$+ \rho \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x^a} \right) \frac{\partial F}{\partial v} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x^a}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial g} \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial g} \right] = \Theta \frac{\partial}{\partial V} \left[\psi_a \phi^a + \nabla_i \phi_a \nabla^i \phi^a \right]$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} (\phi_m \phi^m + V^2) \cdot \frac{\psi_i}{V} + \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\rho} (\ominus 2\phi_i) \right] = + \frac{\psi_i}{V} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v} A \right) \quad \text{I/O}$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_i}{V} \right] \cdot \left(\phi_m \phi^m + V^2 \right) + \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\psi_i}{V} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\phi_m \phi^m + V^2 \right] \ominus \frac{2\sqrt{g}}{\sqrt{g}} \left(\frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial v} \right) \frac{1}{\rho} \oplus \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{\ominus \sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right) \frac{2\phi_i}{\cancel{\rho}} =$$

$$= \frac{\psi_i}{V} \left[2 \frac{\partial \phi_m}{\partial v} \cdot \phi^m + 2V \right] \ominus 2\psi_i \ominus \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\psi_a \phi^a + \nabla_k \phi_a \nabla^k \phi^a \right] 2\phi_i =$$

$$+ \frac{\psi_i}{V} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} A$$

$$= \ominus \left(\frac{\rho \phi_{,i}^a}{V} \right)_{,a} \cdot \left(\phi_m \phi^m + V^2 \right) + \frac{2\rho}{V \cdot \rho} \left(\frac{\partial \phi_m}{\partial v} \right) \cdot \phi^m \cdot \psi_i + \frac{2\psi_i \ominus 2\psi_i}{\cancel{\#} \cancel{\#}} \ominus \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\psi_a \phi^a + \nabla_k \phi_a \nabla^k \phi^a \right] \cdot 2\phi_i =$$

$$= \ominus \left(\frac{\rho \phi_{,i}^a}{V} \right)_{,a} \cdot \left(\phi_m \phi^m + V^2 \right) + \frac{2\rho}{V} \phi^m \cdot \psi_m \cdot \psi_i \ominus \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\psi_m \psi^m + \nabla_k \phi_a \nabla^k \phi^a \right] \cdot 2\phi_i$$

$$+ \frac{\psi_i}{V} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} A \quad + \frac{\psi_i}{V} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} A$$

$$= \ominus \left(\frac{\rho \nabla^a \phi_{,i}}{V} \right)_{,a} \cdot \left(\phi_m \phi^m + V^2 \right) + \frac{2\phi^m \cdot \rho}{V} \cdot \psi_m \cdot \psi_i \ominus \frac{2\phi_i \rho}{V} \left[\psi_m \psi^m + \nabla_k \phi_a \nabla^k \phi^a \right]$$

$\phi_1 \phi_2 \cdot \psi_1$
 $\phi_2 \cdot \phi_1 \cdot \psi_2$?

$$= \ominus \left(\frac{\rho \nabla^a \phi_{,i}}{V} \right)_{,a} \cdot \left(\phi_m \phi^m + V^2 \right) + \frac{2\phi^m \cdot \rho}{V} \cdot \psi_m \cdot \psi_i \ominus \frac{2\phi_i \rho}{V} (\psi_m \psi^m) \ominus \frac{2\phi_i \rho}{V} (\nabla_k \phi_a \nabla^k \phi^a)$$

equal if $[m=i]$!

$$\left[\frac{2\phi^m \cdot \rho}{V} \psi_m \psi_i \ominus \frac{2\phi_i \rho}{V} (\psi_m \psi^m) + \frac{\psi_i}{V} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} A = 0 \right]$$

$$\left(\frac{2\phi_1 \rho}{\sqrt{v}} \psi_2^2\right); \left(\frac{2\rho \phi_2}{\sqrt{v}} \psi_1^2\right)$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} \textcircled{A} \frac{\psi_1}{\sqrt{v}} \right\} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} (\phi_1^2 + v^2) \frac{\psi_1}{\sqrt{v}} \right\} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} (\phi_2^2 + v^2) \frac{\psi_2}{\sqrt{v}} \right\} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} \textcircled{B} \frac{\psi_2}{\sqrt{v}} \right\} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} (\ominus 2\phi_1 \sqrt{g}) \right\} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} (\ominus 2\phi_2 \sqrt{g}) \right\} \right] =$$

$$= \frac{\ominus (\phi_1^2 + v^2) \rho \phi_1^{1\omega}}{\sqrt{v}} \ominus \frac{\ominus (\phi_2^2 + v^2) \rho \phi_2^{1\omega}}{\sqrt{v}} + \boxed{\text{shaded}} \ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \rho}{\sqrt{v}} \psi_2^2 \ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \rho (\phi_2, \omega)^2}{\sqrt{v}} + \\ \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \rho}{\sqrt{v}} \psi_1^2 \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \rho (\phi_1, \omega)^2}{\sqrt{v}}$$

$$\left| \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} \textcircled{A} \frac{\psi_1}{\sqrt{v}} \right\} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} \textcircled{B} \frac{\psi_2}{\sqrt{v}} \right\} \ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \rho}{\sqrt{v}} \psi_2^2 \ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \rho (\phi_2, \omega)^2}{\sqrt{v}} \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \rho \psi_1^2}{\sqrt{v}} \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \rho (\phi_1, \omega)^2}{\sqrt{v}} \right|$$

$$\underbrace{\left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_1}{\sqrt{v}} \right\} \textcircled{A} + \frac{\psi_1}{\sqrt{v}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \textcircled{A} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left\{ \sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_2}{\sqrt{v}} \right\} \textcircled{B} + \frac{\psi_2}{\sqrt{v}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \textcircled{B} \right]}_{\ominus \frac{\rho \phi_1^{1\omega}}{\sqrt{v}} \textcircled{A} \ominus \frac{\rho \phi_2^{1\omega}}{\sqrt{v}} \textcircled{B} + \frac{\psi_1}{\sqrt{v}} \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial v} \right) + \frac{\psi_2}{\sqrt{v}} \left(\frac{\partial B}{\partial v} \right)} \ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \rho}{\sqrt{v}} \psi_2^2 \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \rho \psi_1^2}{\sqrt{v}} + \\ \ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \rho (\phi_2, \omega)^2}{\sqrt{v}} \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \rho (\phi_1, \omega)^2}{\sqrt{v}} =$$

$$= \ominus \underbrace{(\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a}}_{\#} + \underbrace{\frac{2\rho \psi_1^2 \phi_1}{\sqrt{\#}}}_{\#} + \underbrace{\frac{2\rho \phi_2 \psi_1 \psi_2}{\sqrt{\#}}}_{\#} \oplus \underbrace{\frac{2\rho \psi_1^2 \phi_2}{\sqrt{\#}}}_{\#} \oplus \underbrace{\frac{2\rho \psi_1 \phi_2 \psi_2}{\sqrt{\#}}}_{\#} +$$

$$+ \underbrace{\frac{2\rho \psi_2 \phi_1 \psi_1}{\sqrt{\#}}}_{\#} + \underbrace{\frac{2\rho \phi_2 \psi_2^2}{\sqrt{\#}}}_{\#} \oplus \underbrace{\frac{2\rho \psi_2 \psi_1 \phi_2}{\sqrt{\#}}}_{\#} \oplus \underbrace{\frac{2\rho \psi_2 \phi_1}{\sqrt{\#}}}_{\#} +$$

$$\ominus \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} [\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + (\phi_1)_{,a} (\phi_1)^{1a} + (\phi_2)_{,a} (\phi_2)^{1a}] \ominus \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} [\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + (\phi_1)_{,a} (\phi_1)^{1a} + (\phi_2)_{,a} (\phi_2)^{1a}] =$$

$$= \ominus \underbrace{(\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a}}_{\#} + \left(\frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} \phi_2 \psi_1 \psi_2 + \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} \phi_1 \psi_1 \psi_2 + \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} \phi_1 \psi_1 \psi_2 + \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} \phi_2 \psi_1 \psi_2 \right)$$

$$\ominus \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} (\phi_1)_{,a} (\phi_1)^{1a} \ominus \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} (\phi_2)_{,a} (\phi_2)^{1a} \ominus \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} (\phi_1)_{,a} (\phi_1)^{1a} \ominus \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{\#}} (\phi_2)_{,a} (\phi_2)^{1a}$$

$$\ominus \underbrace{(\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a}}_{\#}$$

$$\underbrace{(\phi_1^2 + 2\phi_1 \phi_2 + \phi_2^2)_{,a}}_{\#} = 2\phi_2 \phi_{1,a} + 2\phi_1 \phi_{2,a} + 2\phi_1 \phi_{2,a} + 2\phi_2 \phi_{2,a}$$

$$\underbrace{(\rho \phi_1)_{,a}}_{\#} = \frac{2\rho \phi_1 \phi_{1,a} \phi_{1,a}}{\#} + \frac{2\rho \phi_1 \phi_{1,a} \phi_2}{\#} + \frac{2\rho \phi_1 \rho \phi_{1,a} \phi_{2,a}}{\#} + \frac{2\rho \phi_2 \rho \phi_{1,a} \phi_{2,a}}{\#}$$

$$\underbrace{(\rho \phi_2)_{,a}}_{\#} = \frac{2\rho \phi_1 \phi_{2,a} \phi_{1,a}}{\#} + \frac{2\rho \phi_2 \phi_{2,a} \phi_{2,a}}{\#} + \frac{2\rho \phi_1 \phi_{2,a} \phi_{2,a}}{\#} + \frac{2\rho \phi_2 \rho_{2,a} \phi_{2,a}}{\#}$$

$$(\phi_1^2 \oplus 2\phi_1\phi_2 + \phi_2^2)_{,a} = 2\phi_1 \cdot \phi_{1,a} + 2\phi_2 \cdot \phi_{2,a} \ominus 2\phi_{1,a} \phi_2 \ominus 2\phi_1 \phi_{2,a}$$

$$(\phi_m \cdot \phi^m \ominus 2\varepsilon^{ab} \phi_a \phi_b)_{, \kappa} = \underline{2\phi_{m,\kappa} \cdot \phi^m \ominus 2\varepsilon^{ab} \phi_{a,\kappa} \cdot \phi_b \ominus 2\varepsilon^{ab} \phi_a \phi_{b,\kappa}}$$

all good $\varepsilon^{ab} \phi_a \phi_b \Rightarrow$ only ε^{12} + v2

$$\sum_i \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \left(\phi_m \phi^m \ominus 2\varepsilon^{ab} \phi_a \phi_b \right) \frac{\psi_i}{V} \ominus \frac{2\phi_i \sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right] =$$

$$= \sum_i \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\sqrt{g} \frac{\psi_i}{V} \right) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial \sqrt{g}}{\partial v} \left(\phi_m \phi^m \ominus 2\varepsilon^{ab} \phi_a \phi_b \right) \cdot \frac{\psi_i}{V} \ominus \frac{2}{\rho} \frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial v} \frac{\sqrt{g}}{\sqrt{g}} \oplus \frac{2\phi_i}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\sqrt{g}}{\rho} \right] \right]$$

$$= \sum_i \left[\ominus \left(\rho \phi_i^{,a} \right)_{,a} \text{ (diagonal)} + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial v} \phi_m \right) \cdot \phi^m \cdot 2 \ominus \left(2\sqrt{g} \oplus 2\varepsilon^{ab} \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial v} \cdot \phi_b \ominus 2\varepsilon^{ab} \phi_a \frac{\partial \phi_b}{\partial v} \right) \cdot \frac{\psi_i}{V} + \right.$$

+ $\frac{2\psi_i \rho}{V} [\phi_1 \cdot \psi_1 + \phi_2 \cdot \psi_2 \oplus \psi_1 \cdot \phi_2 \oplus \phi_1 \cdot \psi_2]$
 + $\frac{2\psi_i}{V \rho} [\phi_1 \cdot \psi_1 + \phi_2 \cdot \psi_2 \oplus \psi_1 \cdot \phi_2 \oplus \phi_1 \cdot \psi_2]$

$$\ominus 2\psi_i \oplus \frac{2\phi_i \rho}{V} \left[\psi_m \psi^m + (\phi_m)_{,a} (\phi^m)_{,a} \right] =$$

$$= \ominus \left(\rho \phi_1^{,a} \right)_{,a} \text{ (diagonal)} + \frac{\psi_1}{V} \left[2\phi_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} + 2\phi_2 \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial v} \ominus 2 \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} \cdot \phi_2 \ominus 2\phi_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial v} \right] +$$

$$\ominus \left(\rho \phi_2^{,a} \right)_{,a} \text{ (diagonal)} + \frac{\psi_2}{V} \left[2\phi_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} + 2\phi_2 \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial v} \ominus 2 \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} \cdot \phi_2 \ominus 2\phi_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial v} \right] -$$

we leave with
 $\Rightarrow \frac{2\psi_1 \rho}{V} \phi_2 \psi_2 + \frac{2\psi_2 \rho}{V} \phi_1 \psi_1$
 $+ \frac{2\psi_1 \rho}{V} \phi_1 \psi_1 + \frac{2\psi_2 \rho}{V} \phi_2 \psi_2$
 $= \frac{4\psi_1 \rho}{V} (\psi_1 \psi_2) + \frac{4\psi_2 \rho}{V} (\psi_1 \psi_2)$

$$\ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \rho}{V} \left[\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + (\phi_1)_{,a} (\phi_1)^{,a} + (\phi_2)_{,a} (\phi_2)^{,a} \right] \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \rho}{V} \left[\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + (\phi_1)_{,a} (\phi_1)^{,a} + (\phi_2)_{,a} (\phi_2)^{,a} \right]$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} (\gamma \phi_1^2 + v^2) \frac{\psi_1}{v} \ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right] \Rightarrow \ominus \frac{(\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a}}{v} (\phi_1^2 \gamma + v^2) \ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \gamma \rho}{v} \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} (\gamma \phi_2^2 + v^2) \frac{\psi_2}{v} \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right] \Rightarrow \ominus \frac{(\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a}}{v} (\phi_2^2 \gamma + v^2) \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \gamma \rho}{v} \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}$$

$$\ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \gamma \rho}{v} (\psi_2^2 + \phi_{2,a} \phi_2^{1a}) \rightarrow \frac{(\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a}}{v} \rightarrow \left(\frac{\psi_2}{v} \right)_{,v}$$

$$\ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \gamma \rho}{v} (\psi_1^2 + \phi_{1,a} \phi_1^{1a}) \rightarrow \frac{(\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a}}{v} \rightarrow \left(\frac{\psi_1}{v} \right)_{,v}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \left(\frac{\phi_1^2}{v} \right) \frac{\psi_1}{v} \right]} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\frac{\psi_1}{v} \sqrt{g'} \right] \cdot \phi_1^2 + \frac{\psi_1}{v} \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} (\phi_1^2) = \ominus \frac{(\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a}}{v} \phi_1^2 + \frac{2\phi_1}{v} \frac{\partial \phi_1 \rho}{\partial v} \psi_1 =$$

$$= \frac{\ominus (\rho \phi_1^{1a})_{,a} \phi_1^2 + 2\phi_1 \rho \psi_1^2}{v}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \left(\frac{\phi_2^2}{v} \right) \frac{\psi_2}{v} \right]} = \frac{\ominus (\rho \phi_2^{1a})_{,a} \phi_2^2 + 2\phi_2 \rho \psi_2^2}{v}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \left(\ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right) \right]} = \ominus 2 \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial v} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{1}{\rho} + 2\phi_1 \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\ominus \frac{\sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right] = \ominus 2\psi_1 \ominus \frac{2\phi_1 \rho}{v} \left[\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a}^2 + \phi_{2,a}^2 \right]$$

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left[\sqrt{g} \left(\ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \sqrt{g'}}{\rho} \right) \right]} = \ominus 2\psi_2 \ominus \frac{2\phi_2 \rho}{v} \left[\psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \phi_{1,a}^2 + \phi_{2,a}^2 \right]$$